

volume was made up to 10 ml with double-distilled water. This solution was aspirated to AAS and the amount of copper was determined from the calibration curve. The method was applied for the determination of copper in different blood samples (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN HUMAN BLOOD SAMPLES

Sample no.	Copper, $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	
	Direct aspiration	Proposed method
1	10.0	1.60
2	4.5	1.29
3	4.5	1.29
4	1.6	0.80
5	2.0	0.96
6	2.4	1.12

Results and Discussion

Copper was quantitatively extracted in the pH range 7.0–8.5. The quantitative extraction of copper mostly occurs with benzene, chloroform, cyclohexane and toluene, the extraction being 100%. Copper has been completely stripped back from organic layer to aqueous layer containing 0.03–3.00 *N* HCl. A shaking period of 1 min for extraction and a shaking period of 15 s for back-extraction have been found to be enough. On the other hand, 2 min were allowed for settling the equilibrium in case of extraction or back-extraction. Extraction of 50 ppm copper was increased with exchanger concentration and was complete at 1.6×10^{-3} mM. It has been found that the calibration curve of copper obtained by the general procedure is linear over the range 0.5–9.0 ppm. The stoichiometry of the extracted species has been found to be $\text{Cu}(\text{LCE})_2$.

Separation of copper from diverse ions: The extraction of a definite amount of copper (5 ppm) in presence of various ions (amount in parenthesis in ppm) was examined under experimental condition within an error of $\pm 2\%$ and the results are as follows: Na^+ , K^+ (8000); Li^+ (5000); Rb^+ , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} (2000); Ca^{2+} (1800); Cs^+ (1500); Ag^+ (350); Sn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} (50); Fe^{3+} (20); Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} (10); Mn^{2+} (8); Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} (6); Mg^{2+} , Ni^{2+} (5); large amounts of F^- , Cl^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , CrO_4^{2-} , MoO_4^{2-} do not interfere. The method was actually tested for copper extraction in the following synthetic mixtures (amount in parenthesis in ppm): (a) Li^+ , MoO_4^{2-} (1000); (b) Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} (5); (c) Mn^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} (5); (d) Mg^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Fe^{3+} (5); (e) Ag^+ , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} (50).

In case of direct aspiration of the sample solution to AAS, high values for copper were obtained due to interference of large amounts of iron² and sodium⁸ present in blood (Table 1). The efficiency of the method in releasing copper from blood was

assessed by adding known amounts of copper to untreated blood samples, wet ashing them and determining the recoveries (97.5–102.5%) of the analyte.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Prof. C. R. Maity, Burdwan Medical College, for supplying the blood samples, and are thankful to Shell Chemical Co., London, for gift samples of Versatic-10.

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Inhibition of Corrosion of Mild Steel in Aqueous Solution of Chloride by Chromate†

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Manuscript received 5 August 1985, revised 16 July 1987, accepted 13 November 1987

METALS when immersed completely in water tend to corrode because of their thermodynamic instability^{1–3}. Chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions are particularly aggressive. Sanyal and Nigam⁴ reported corrosion of mild steel in alcohol solution. Best and Roche⁵ investigated the use of chromate as inhibitor for ethanol, methanol, isopropanol and ethylene glycol. Chromate has been used effectively as inhibitor⁶ for brass in cooling water system. Sanyal and Grover⁷ showed that sodium nitrite and sodium chromate can be used as inhibitors for mild steel in water mains at 40°.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the corrosion of mild steel and the influence of chromate on it.

Experimental

Metal specimens, their preparation, the methods of measurement of corrosion rate, potential, percent-

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tage inhibition and polarisation were the same as described earlier⁹. All experiments were conducted at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$) unless otherwise stated.

Results and Discussion

The effect of concentration of chromate on its inhibition efficiency in aqueous solution of fixed concentration ($10^{-1} M$) of sodium chloride is shown in Fig. 1. The metal losses were progressively decreased with the rise in concentration of chromate. The potentials were ennobled in the presence of the inhibitor and the potential-concentration curve closely follows the weight loss-concentration curve.

Fig. 1. Effect of chromate concentration on weight loss and potential of mild steel in $10^{-1} M$ NaCl (for 1 month at $30 \pm 2^\circ$): (O) weight loss and (x) potential.

Table 1 shows the weight loss of mild steel in different concentrations (10^{-4} – $10^{-1} M$) of sodium chloride solution in the presence and absence of

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF NaCl CONCENTRATION ON CORROSION OF MILD STEEL CONTAINING K_2CrO_4
Duration = 30 days, Temp. = $30 \pm 2^\circ$

Concn. of NaCl M	Weight loss ($mg\ dm^{-2}$)*			
	NaCl	NaCl+0.01% chromate	NaCl+0.1% chromate	NaCl+3% chromate
10^{-4}	921.95 (—)	21.95 (97.61)	Nil (100.00)	Nil (100.00)
10^{-3}	946.34 (—)	95.12 (89.94)	24.39 (97.42)	Nil (100.00)
10^{-2}	1 085.36 (—)	227.64 (79.02)	141.69 (86.94)	Nil (100.00)
10^{-1}	1 260.97 (—)	329.84 (78.84)	222.99 (82.31)	Nil (100.00)

*Values in parenthesis represent percentage inhibition.

chromate. It shows that higher concentration of anion required larger amount of inhibitor.

The effect of temperature (30 – 80°) on the corrosion of mild steel in the presence and absence of chromate in $10^{-1} M$ sodium chloride is shown in Table 2. Chromate maintained its excellent inhibitive effect over the entire temperature range. Its increased efficiency at higher temperature is of interest and may be attributed to increased chemisorption⁹⁻¹¹ of the chromate enabling the formation of a protective oxide film¹²⁻¹⁵.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON CORROSION OF MILD STEEL IN $10^{-1} M$ NaCl CONTAINING K_2CrO_4

Duration = 1 day

Temp. $^\circ C$	Weight loss ($mg\ dm^{-2}$)*			
	$10^{-1} M$ NaCl	NaCl+0.1% chromate	NaCl+0.5% chromate	NaCl+1% chromate
30	56.09 (—)	8.35 (85.11)	5.57 (90.25)	Nil (100.00)
40	75.00 (—)	11.78 (84.29)	7.5 (90.00)	Nil (100.00)
60	111.90 (—)	15.54 (86.15)	10.05 (91.02)	Nil (100.00)
80	151.22 (—)	20.03 (87.29)	12.01 (92.72)	Nil (100.00)

*Values in parenthesis represent percentage inhibition.

Arrhenius plots for uninhibited and inhibited system are rectilinear and the activation energies calculated from the slopes of the curves are $4.10\ kcal\ mol^{-1}$ for $10^{-1} M$ NaCl, $4.33\ kcal\ mol^{-1}$ for $10^{-1} M$ NaCl+0.1% chromate, and $5.69\ kcal\ mol^{-1}$ for $10^{-1} M$ NaCl+0.5% chromate.

Weight loss of metal for various periods of immersion (5–30 days) in $10^{-1} M$ sodium chloride solution with and without inhibitor are shown in the Table 3. Chromate was effective in long test duration giving good percentage of protection in all cases. However, the requirement of inhibitor concentration was increased in longer test duration as expected.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF PERIOD OF IMMERSION ON CORROSION OF MILD STEEL IN $10^{-1} M$ NaCl CONTAINING K_2CrO_4

Temp. = $30 \pm 2^\circ$

Time day	Weight loss ($mg\ dm^{-2}$)*			
	10^{-1} NaCl	NaCl+0.1% chromate	NaCl+0.5% chromate	NaCl+3% chromate
5	134.44 (—)	19.84 (85.21)	10.26 (92.35)	Nil (100.00)
10	365.85 (—)	56.29 (84.61)	26.24 (93.63)	Nil (100.00)
20	824.85 (—)	126.46 (84.67)	52.31 (93.67)	Nil (100.00)
30	1 260.97 (—)	222.99 (82.31)	63.41 (94.97)	Nil (100.00)

*Values in parenthesis represent percentage inhibition.

Anodic and cathodic polarisation curves for mild steel in $10^{-1} M$ sodium chloride solution with

and without inhibitor are shown in Fig. 2. It will be seen that in the absence of any inhibitor there is both cathodic and anodic polarisation but the anodic polarisation is considerably increased in presence of inhibitor. The polarisation measurements indicate that chromate controls the anodic process. High polarisation of the anodes at low current densities indicate film formation at the

Fig. 2. Polarisation of mild steel in (O) uninhibited and (x) inhibited 10^{-1} M NaCl solution.

anode sites. The protective effect of chromate is due to the formation of passive film^{16,17}. Rajagopalan *et al.*¹⁸ also proved the formation of a passive film by chromate by electron diffraction, radio-tracer and cathodic reduction techniques. The Tafel parameters and inhibitor efficiency were calculated¹⁹ and are given in Table 4. The inhibition efficiency calculated from Tafel parameters (99.99%) is in close

TABLE 4—TAFEL PARAMETERS AND INHIBITION EFFICIENCY

Solution	Tafel slope (anodic)	Corrosion current of anodic Tafel line mA cm ⁻²	Inhibitor efficiency (%)	
			From anodic Tafel line	From wt. loss method
10^{-1} M NaCl	0.30	1×10^{-1}	—	—
10^{-1} M NaCl + 3% chromate	0.16	1×10^{-5}	99.99	100.00

agreement with the value (100%) calculated from weight loss measurements.

Conclusion: The corrosion of mild steel is reduced and the potential ennobled as the concentration of chromate is increased in aqueous solution of chloride. Chromate remained effective at high temperature (upto 80°) and for long test durations. The mechanism of the action of the inhibitor in aqueous solution of chloride indicates that it is an anodic inhibitor.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.S.) is grateful to late Prof. S. S. P. Verma, Ex-Principal, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj, for facilities. Thanks are due to Prof. K. D. Banerji, Professor and Head, P. G. Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur, for keen interest and encouragement.

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Effect of Natural Products isolated from Three Species of Sida on some Gram-positive and Gram-negative Bacteria

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Manuscript received 1 July 1987, revised 25 September 1987, accepted 3 November 1987

BALAS, the different species of *Sida*, (fam: *Malvaceae*) are well known as valuable drugs in Ayurvedic and Unani systems of medicine. Considering their medicinal uses¹⁻³, three species of this genus, i.e. *Sida acuta* Burm., *S. veronicaefolia* Lam. and *S. rhombifolia* Linn. have been selected in order to find out the active constituents of these plants against some gram-positive and some gram-negative bacteria.